

PECULIARITIES OF USING GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *Present article is about peculiarities of games and their role in teaching foreign languages. Types of game activities and their advantages in the process of teaching foreign languages are mentioned in the article. Besides some approaches of how to organize games are also suggested.*

Key words: *teaching foreign languages, using games in teaching, playing in pairs, motivating, language skills, cognitive styles.*

The resolution of the President of Uzbekistan “On measures to further improve system of foreign languages teaching” dated from 10 December 2012 is being actively implemented in our republic.

This document serves as an important guideline in development of new textbooks for teaching foreign languages, introduction of advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies, education of a new generation to foreign languages, cardinal improvement of the system of training of specialists, fluent in these languages, creation of conditions and opportunities for wide use of information resources by students.

Persistent works on raising awareness of the public concerning the essence and significance of the resolution, ensuring its execution are being carried out.

At present the most topical issues of reforms in the area of language teaching is in the creation of convenient methodology for learners of English and other foreign languages starting from the earliest days of education. As it was mentioned above English and other foreign languages are being taught from the first classes of public schools. Moreover, there are many preschool education establishments that give lessons on foreign languages in our country. In spite of the huge amount of preschool establishments that teach English as a foreign language there is still need for a consistent and continuing methodology that will ensure preparation of pupils’ foreign language skills before elementary education is started.

There are many statements about using games in teaching, e.g. games are not serious, these are only time-fillers, games could be used only outside a classroom, games are disruptive, or that children will use their mother tongue when playing a game and

gain no benefit in English. But using games and activities in teaching very young English learners start from the attitude of children towards learning. As Brumfit claims, children learn through playing, they interact, so develop their language skills. "It is a commonplace that young children learn better through play or at least can be induced to go along with teaching that is tempered by "fun" activities." [1]

When using games in teaching, it is necessary to understand what does the expression "game" means. Brumfit defines games as: "Games are activities governed by rules, which set up clearly defined goal. The achievement of these goals signals the end of the game.

Games involve a contest either between players or between the players and the goal, and games should lead to having fun. Games are for playing, and this element of play is crucial."

Before using games and "fun" activities, it is needed to monitor the class and develop a clear understanding of the mechanics and effects of various activity types.

Some games are called "drill-like" where it is necessary to use some "fun" elements; on the other hand, some games allow children to use their mother tongue. The teacher could choose from various types or games where it is necessary to use some material or equipment, e.g. card games, board games, paper and pencil games, blackboard games or box games. Children could play games in pairs, in groups, in teams, with the whole class against the teacher. Playing in pairs involve more learners in oral interaction and demand that the children co-operate each other, so the language must be used flexibly, well within the child's limits. By all means, it is a teacher who considers which game to use, what the right time to use it is, how to link it up with the syllabus, books or programme, and how each game will benefit children in different ways.

The focus of the games should be at speaking or listening, with major focus on pronunciation. [1]

Children naturally and universally engage in games and when they are involved in one they are eager to play, they create a powerful need to use the language by nature.

Playing a game is an authentic opportunity for language use for children. The natures of the games changes as children develop, ranging through ritual, competition, fantasy and luck. Games could be motivating for children, and the emphasis of motivation is on conflicting forces of "instrumental" motivation and "integrative" motivation, where the "instrumental" motivation focuses on developing of the competence in the language for reason; and the "integrative" motivation focuses on "establishing closer links with the language community within which the language is used." For younger children learning a foreign language is the motivation deriving from parental and social attitudes weaker than that one from the classroom itself. In the classroom children have more opportunities to develop their knowledge of the foreign language because they could

negotiate the meaning for being sure they understand properly what has been said, so they develop the language skills more rapidly. On the whole children like games with luck element which adds excitement to them and reduces the socially divisive nature of “clever” games. These games could become tiring when the same players are repeatedly winning, and reducing the level of involvement of players. The games could be driven by competition between players or co-operation, in some cases by both together. Many games are competitive whereunto it is important that co-operation encourages verbal negotiation.

Play is the crucial feature used in English lessons, encouraging all aspects of development. Physical development may be supported by using manipulative skills, TPR activities, drawing and running, jumping or dancing. Making decisions and solving problems or tasks benefits cognitive development. Language development involves participating, sharing and co-operating in natural and meaningful language-acquisition activities. It is good to work in a friendly atmosphere, where children play alongside with other pupils, are able to follow the instructions or lead; and this definitely contributes to social development. Children need to be encouraged during their work (according to my methodology by stickers they receive every lesson, by some sweets or just by praise commenting on their efforts) which makes them satisfied and pride contributing positively to emotional development. The last but not least, by taking into account some moral rules, being fair and helpful to the others, the concept of spiritual development is maintained.

Activities taking into account children’s differences need to be designed properly addressing this diversity and enabling each child to develop their abilities to the maximum. Learners with right-brain dominance who work well with movement or feelings need to be catered as well as left-brain learners showing talent for logic. Learners’ differences may involve their age, gender (boys prefer different kinds of activities than girls), intelligence, maturity, concentration span, specific learning difficulties, cognitive styles associated with mental development and capability to take a certain amount of information, learning styles, learner autonomy, the knowledge of L1 and an aptitude for languages, family background and socio-economic status, interests and preferences, spiritual development and beliefs, the group factor associated with group dynamics and the mood of children and the overall atmosphere.

REFERENCES:

1. Brumfit, Christopher, Jayne Moon, and Ray Tongue. Teaching English to Children: From Practice to Principle. London: Harper Collins Publishers, 1991.

2. Jalolov J.J., Makhkamova G.T., Ashurov Sh. S. English Language Teaching Methodology (theory and practice). Tashkent, 2015.

3. E. E Hamdamov. Technology Forming the Gnostic Competence of Future Teachers of Foreign Language, Bulletin of Gulistan State University: Vol- 1. 2021.